

Accelerating Progressive Damage and Failure Analysis of Composites using a Hybrid Implicit-Explicit Approach

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1. Numerical Accuracy, Efficiency, and Robustness in Progressive Damage and Failure Analysis (PDFA)
2. **HIMEX: Hybrid Implicit-Explicit** PDFA
3. Application Examples: Open-hole Tension
4. Discussions
5. Conclusions and Vision

1. Accuracy, Efficiency, and Robustness in PDFA

Multiscale Composite Damage

Structural

Macro

Micro

Progressive Damage Analysis across Length Scales

Waas, A., 2022. The case for more virtual testing. AEROSPACE AMERICA, 60(6), pp.22-24.

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1. Accuracy, Efficiency, and Robustness in PDFA

<https://simulation-blog.technia.com/simulation/implicit-vs-explicit-finite-element-analysis>

<https://featips.com/2022/09/29/implicit-vs-explicit-analysis/>

	Implicit PDFA (Backward Euler)	Explicit PDFA (Forward Euler)
Stable time increment size	Large	Small, proper mass scaling may be used
Analysis Accuracy	High	High only when sufficiently small time increment is used
Analysis Efficiency	High	Low
Analysis Robustness	Low	High, more suitable for damage propagation analysis
Abaqus subroutine implementation	Request Jacobian, stress, and state variable updates	Request stress, and state variable updates

1. Accuracy, Efficiency, and Robustness in PDFA

- Most of the OHT loading history (**Stage I**) is without damage initiation or propagation.
- At **stage II**, minimal matrix damage and delamination start to happen.
- At **stage III**, extensive damage of all the three modes keep growing, leading to the final catastrophic failure.
- **Most of the OHT analyses are done with explicit PDFA.** Some implicit PDFA may be conducted but most likely convergent until the beginning of **stage III** -- **no extensive damage propagation could be effectively predicted by implicit PDFA.**

1. Accuracy, Efficiency, and Robustness in PDFA

Analogy: Driving on a smooth and flat highway with high gears

- **Smooth:** Low numerical difficulty (e.g., low material and geometry nonlinearity, minimal damage)
- **High gears:** Fast **implicit solver**

- Fast implicit PDFA analysis **only applicable** to Stage I and partially Stage II.

1. Accuracy, Efficiency, and Robustness in PDFA

Load-displacement

Damage development

Analogy: Driving on a rugged uphill road with low gears

- **Rugged:** High numerical difficulty (e.g., damage propagation)
- **Low gears:** Slow and robust **explicit solver**

- Robust explicit PDFA applies to all the stages, but **not necessary for stage I.**

1. Accuracy, Efficiency, and Robustness in PDFA

- Many PDFA analysis cases (e.g., OHT/OHC, single-edge notched tension, compression after impact, etc.) are initially and majorly with no or minimal damage initiation and propagation, followed by drastic/catastrophic damage propagation.
- Elastic implicit stress analysis is applicable to the undamaged stage for high efficiency. When damage is about to happen, explicit PDFA is activated to predict damage evolution and structural failure.
- The key questions are **how and when to transfer from implicit analysis to explicit analysis**.

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2. HIMEX: Hybrid Implicit-Explicit PDFA

- Implicit stress analysis → state transferring → explicit PDFA.
- For most quasi-static testing of composites, **only one** "switching gear" is needed. Therefore, HIMEX may not be applied to impact or fatigue analyses yet.
- Deformed **geometry**, full-field **strains**, and **stresses** are to be transferred from the implicit stress analysis to the explicit PDFA.

2. HIMEX: Hybrid Implicit-Explicit PDFA: Deformation Transferring

Implicit Stress Analysis

Explicit PDFA: starting with a deformed mesh

- Implicit stress analysis is the first step of HIMEX.
- Deformation transferring is ensured by **importing nodal coordinates of the deformed mesh** at the end of the implicit analysis to the explicit PDFA mesh.
- Deformation interpolation can be achieved **between different meshes**, enhancing the flexibility of HIMEX.
- Explicit PDFA starts with a deformed mesh and **pre-existing stresses and strains** need to be imported.
- A **semi-automated Python script** has been developed to facilitate fast deformation transferring.

2. HIMEX: Hybrid Implicit-Explicit PDFA: Stress and Strain Transferring

Implicit Stress Analysis

Stress states imported from the end of the implicit analysis

Explicit PDFA:
starting with pre-existing stresses and strains

- Stress transferring is ensured by **importing stresses from the integration points** of the implicit mesh to the corresponding **integration points** of the explicit mesh.
- Strain transferring is ensured by calculating the pre-existing strains of the PDFA model by:

$$\{\epsilon^{pre}\} = [S]\{\sigma^{pre}\}.$$

where, $[S]$ is the elastic **compliance matrix**.

- A **semi-automated Python script** has been developed to facilitate fast **stress transferring**.
- The PDFA model enhanced Schapery theory (EST) **has been modified** to facilitate fast **strain transferring**.

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3. Application Example: OHT – Model and Mesh

C3D8R elements
 HIMEX Analysis
 Mass scaling target time increment 1e-5 s

0°- or 90°-ply mesh

45°- or -45°-ply mesh

Fine: 0.5 ~ 0.6 mm, Coarse: 2 mm

3. Application Example: OHT – PDFA Model EST

Damage modes of 3D EST

Matrix transverse tensile/compressive damage

Matrix in-plane shear damage

Matrix transverse shear damage

- Enhanced Schapery Theory (EST) combines Schapery Theory (ST) (Schapery, 1989) and the Bazant-Oh Crack Band (CB) (Bazant, 1983) model to analyze the intra-ply damage and failure of a lamina
- Implemented with Abaqus VUMAT.

3. Application Example: OHT Results [25/50/25] Layup

- **Max time saving: 26.5%**
- **No accuracy loss.**

3. Application Example: OHT Results [50/40/10] Layup

- **Max time saving: 29.5%**
- **No accuracy loss.**

3. Application Example: OHT Results: Damage History of the [25/50/25] Layup

Explicit PDFA All Through: 151 mins

HIMEX: Implicit analysis (29 mins) + Explicit PDFA (82 mins)

- The predicted damage development histories are highly similar.
- Snapshots of damage taken at slightly different time due to the mismatch of starting points.

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4. Discussions: Numerical Oscillations induced by HIMEX

- After the implicit-explicit transitioning, **numerical oscillations** are seen. The later the transition, the higher the oscillations.
- The numerical oscillations are likely to be induced by 1) **precision** of stress and strain transferring. 2) **damage initiates** shortly after transition, and 3) exact **force equilibrium** is inherently **not ensured** in explicit analysis.

4. Discussions: When to “Switch Gears” in HIMEX

HIMEX implicit-explicit transition at delamination initiation (after matrix damage initiation and before fiber damage) is optimal

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5. Conclusions

- A new **hybrid implicit-explicit (HIMEX)** PDFA framework has been developed to accelerate the PDFA. HIMEX leverages the advantages of both the implicit (high efficiency) and explicit (robustness) algorithms.
- Demonstrated by the OHT application cases, HIMEX **saves the computation time up to 29.5% without compromising accuracy.**
- HIMEX is **transferrable across analysis software packages and PDFA subroutines**, generally applicable to quasi-static damage analysis of composites (e.g., OHT/OHC, SENT, SLP, DCB/ENF/MMB, etc.)
- Future directions include applying HIMEX to more complex cases (e.g., postbuckling and CAI) and developing HIMEX with **multiple explicit-implicit transitioning** for fatigue analysis.

Thank you, Question?

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